

LIFE21-NAT-IT-LIFE DREAM

Deep REef restoration And litter removal in the Mediterranean sea

LIFE DREAM Data Management Plan

D1.1

Attachment: LIFE DREAM Data Policy

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	3
1. Data summary	4
1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?.....	4
1.2. What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?	5
1.3. Will you re-use any existing data and how?	7
1.4. What is the origin of the data?	7
1.5. What is the expected size of the data?	8
1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?	8
2. FAIR data	8
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	11
2.2. Making data openly accessible	11
2.3. Making data interoperable	12
2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	13
3. Allocation of resources	13
4. Data security	14
5. Ethical aspects	16
6. Other issues	16
ANNEX I	18

INTRODUCTION

Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of a good data management. This document describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated in the framework of the LIFE DREAM Project, including: i) data acquisition or production during the project; ii) how to manage, describe and store LIFE DREAM data and which standards to use, and iii) how to handle and protect LIFE DREAM data during and after the completion of the project. As part of making scientific research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR), a DMP should include information on:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project;
- which data will be collected, processed and/or generated;
- which methodology and standards will be applied;
- whether data will be shared/made open access;
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

DMP intends to be a living document, agreed among the partners, where information can be made available on a finer level of granularity through updates as the implementation of the project progresses and when significant changes occur. This document represents the first release of the LIFE DREAM DMP due month 12, expected to be constantly updated during the lifespan of the Project.

LIFE DREAM DMP follows the Horizon 2020 FAIR Data Management Plan Template (H2020 Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, Version 3.0, 26 July 2016).

As a separate attachment to the DMP, the LIFE DREAM **Data policy** has been designed. The procedures described in the LIFE DREAM data policy shall be followed by all members of the consortium and ensure that: i) data on human subjects are transferred and used in a secure setting; ii) the use of data is compliant with ethical-legal requirements (including signed informed consent, ethics approval, and the applicable data protection laws, furthermore the EU data protection regulation, which is applicable from May 2018); and iii) the use of both existing and new data occurs in agreement with the Data Owner/Data Provider.

1. Data summary

Points to be addressed:

- What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?
- Will you re-use any existing data and how?
- What is the origin of the data?
- What is the expected size of the data?
- To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

A specific objective of the LIFE DREAM Project is improving the knowledge base about **Deep Reefs** (DR) and **human activities** in four Project Areas (PAs) in the Mediterranean Sea:

1. Monopoli shelf and Bari Canyon (Apulian margin) in the South Adriatic Sea;
2. Dohrn Canyon (Gulf of Naples) in the Tyrrhenian Sea;
3. Seco de los Olivos Seamount in the Alboran Sea;
4. National Marine Park of Alonissos Northern Sporades in the Aegean Sea.

After a knowledge review during the proposal drafting, LIFE DREAM identified gaps both in terms of spatial distribution and resolution of data in the four PAs. The knowledge gaps identified will be covered during the Project by gathering new data through oceanographic campaigns, mapping and assessing human activities, and performing a multi-criteria analysis. The objectives of the data collection/generation are i) developing a holistic overview of the DR ecosystems; ii) filling the gaps of knowledge, iii) providing a baseline to evaluate DR health status, and iv) planning the area-based conservation actions, iv) designating new N2K sites for DR, considering a set of alternative options, and providing recommendations in the management plan.

1.2. What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

The data collected and generated during the LIFE DREAM Project can be grouped in **three categories**:

- previous data;
- collected data;
- generated data.

Furthermore, they be clustered into **six typologies**:

1. **Documentation material**: transcripts and agendas of meetings, reports, deliverables, milestones, scientific publications, leaflets, brochures, LIFE DREAM Technical Protocol (.docx, .pdf, .rtf), documents, and reports;
2. **Compiled data**: a review of already existing spatial data has been performed during the drafting phase of the LIFE DREAM proposal. We collected data from open regional, national and European spatial geoportals (.shp, .geotif, .ascii, .gdb), bibliography (.pdf), previous projects (.shp, .geotif, .ascii, .pdf, .jpg, .mp4), and LIFE DREAM beneficiaries (.shp, .geotif, .xls, .txt, .kml, .kmz, .pdf, .jpg, .mp4). The Project will create the baseline knowledge for the implementation of the activities planned in the four PAs, in particular the following data will be homogenized and integrated:
 - geophysical data (e.g., bathymetry, seabed acoustic reflectivity, sub-bottom profiles);
 - geological data (e.g., bottom samples, videos and images);
 - biological data on deep reefs characterising the PAs (e.g., species occurrences, spatial distribution of the habitats, samples, videos and images);
 - oceanographic variables (e.g., temperature anomalies, currents);
 - type and distribution of all human activities and pressures carried out within the Project Areas and/or impacting on them (e.g., fishing activities, maritime traffic, shellfish and fish farms);

- Marine Litter (ML) sources at basin scale (Adriatic Sea, Tyrrhenian Sea, and Aegean Sea) or in areas adjacent to the study sites;
 - legislation provisions for the study areas and potential administrative gaps;
 - management plan and maritime spatial planning actions;
 - socio-economic data using NUTS 2 and NUTS 3 indicators if available (e.g., on basic demographics, socioeconomic status, employment, income etc).
3. **Field data:** environmental data, marine litter data, prototype operational data, etc. During the oceanographic cruises, LIFE DREAM will collect geophysics data (.all, .ascii), and physical samples (e.g., water samples, corals samples, or sediment/substrate samples); following the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) monitoring protocols, the Project will carry on at least 6 ROV transects (200 m each) per site (13 considering all PAs) producing images (.tif, .jpg), and videos (.mp4, .mov, .mts).
4. **Processed data:** video/image analysis, samples analysis, marine litter data analysis, analysis of the recycled material and recycling process, etc. (.xls, .csv, .txt). Production of information to assess the DR health status following the MSFD indicators:
- species richness observed along a transect, based on the identification of benthic organisms at the lowest possible taxonomic rank;
 - relative abundance of each structuring species (*sensu* Habitats Directive, see section B2b), expressed in number of colonies/individuals per m² of hard substrate present along the transect, excluding substrates of different nature;
 - health status of structuring species, calculated as the percentage of epibiosis and/or necrosis and entrapment, taking note of the following aspects:
 - percentage of colonies/individuals presenting the phenomenon in the population;
 - extent of the phenomenon on individual colonies/individuals as a percentage of the area affected per species (<25%, 25%-50%; 50%-75%; >75%);
 - number of colonies/individuals of structuring species clearly affected by the presence of ML;

- height measurements of the colonies/individuals present along the transect (measuring, when possible, a minimum of 30 and a maximum of 100 colonies/individuals for each species), in order to provide estimates of population size structure per species per site;
 - abundance and type of ML and physical damage (fishing or other anthropogenic activities) along the transect.
5. **Cartographic products:** high resolution maps of spatial distribution of DR ecosystem, maps and assessment of human activities in the PAs (e.g., fishing activities, maritime traffic), multiple uses maps, and maps resulting from multi-criteria analysis (MCA), in particular: i) areas deserving protection through the enlargement/proposal of N2K sites; ii) areas characterized by multiple stressors; iii) areas of conflicts between human uses and conservation measures.
6. **Other products:** data for LIFE DREAM Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to quantify project's impact on different premises: socioeconomics of the areas surrounding the PAs, stakeholders involvements, increasing awareness among stakeholders and general public.

1.3. Will you re-use any existing data and how?

LIFE DREAM will re-use already existing spatial data about Deep Reefs (DR), human activities and pressures at Project Area (PA) scale. The data will be integrated in a WebGIS and will be available for all the project partners as background to organize the activities at sea, to fill in the Standard Data Forms (SDF) for the Natura 2000 designation, and to perform the Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA).

1.4. What is the origin of the data?

The origin of the data can be classified in **four categories**:

- project beneficiaries, affiliated entities and other participants;
- already existing database, freely accessible through the web;

- previous research projects;
- oceanographic campaigns.

1.5. What is the expected size of the data?

The LIFE DREAM Project expects to manage digital data for about 4 TB.

1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

All collected and generated data will be shared among LIFE DREAM partners, covering a wide range of scientific disciplines from ecology to oceanography, to geophysics and geology, anthropic impacts, habitat modelling and mapping, but also involving governmental and Non-Governmental Organisations dealing with fishery and socio-economic impact of natural resources. Some products of the Project have a socioeconomic value and could be reused by local, regional and national entities and policy makers (e.g., Governors of municipalities and regions and MPA managers).

2. FAIR data

Points to be addressed:

- In general terms, your research data should be 'FAIR' that is findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. These principles precede implementation choices and do not necessarily suggest any specific technology, standard or implementation-solution.

Data will be gathered and managed by the Data Manager (DM) from the LIFE DREAM partners, who must provide the following information for each dataset:

- Dataset Name: the name of the dataset
- Data Type: see previous categorization
- Data Format: e.g., .jpg, .tif, .pdf
- Data Provider: e.g., Copernicus, CERN, CNR
- Data Source: e.g., satellite, field activity, scientific paper
- Data Access rights: only for internal usage, public
- Data size classes: e.g., < 100 MB, 100 MB to 1 GB, > 1GB

- Whenever available or feasible we also collect this optional information:
- Spatial resolution (if applicable)
- Temporal resolution (if applicable)
- Temporal coverage available
- Data Availability
- Metadata Available
- Standards applied

All data collected and generated during the LIFE DREAM Project activities will be stored in a relational spatial database, to best manage the information and organise further steps of the project, and will be published through a WebGIS, accessible to partners, stakeholders and general public. In detail, all information (spatial and non-spatial data) collected during the lifespan of the Project, and 5 years after its end will be managed through the CNR Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) which consists of several elements: software and hardware, spatial data, metadata, web services, data storage and standards. The data and the products of the LIFE DREAM Project will be homogenized and standardized through a Geodatabase (implemented using ArcGIS software following the INSPIRE Data Specifications), a spatial relational database made of the spatial component (where) and their attributes (what). The data will be grouped into layers, according to the individual components with similar features (points, lines, polygons), and the layers will be organized by themes (e.g., Protected sites, Habitats, Oceanography). Once the Geodatabase is populated, it will be moved into an ORACLE database on the CNR server (ArcGIS server). The layers will be catalogued through the Content Management System Moka (® Semenda srl) using adequate symbologies, and published in a HTML5 web APP application (CMS Moka and ArcGIS server), obtaining the LIFE DREAM Geoportal. The geoportal is a key element for the project, used to access the geographic information and the associated geographic services via browser (e.g., visualize, query, filter, measure, print a map). It allows the partners to share data and results, and to disclose them outside the project. The geoportal will be accessible through the LIFE DREAM website (<https://www.life-dream.eu/>), together with the Web Map Services (WMS), that are OGC web services allowing the direct visualization of the layers in a desktop GIS environment. The OGC services will ensure the interoperability of the system. Datasets, layers and WMS will

be described by metadata ISO 19115, an internationally-adopted schema for describing geographic information and services, providing information about data: Title, Abstract, Author, Keywords, Extent, Data policy, Source, Lineage, etc. All metadata will be available through the ISMAR metadata catalogue, a mechanism for storing and accessing descriptive metadata, allowing users to discover LIFE DREAM data and products on the web. The LIFE DREAM Geoportal will store and integrate all data, products and results collected during the lifespan of the Project and for the following five years after its ends. Furthermore, all the data gathered will be transferred to European databases, such as EMODnet (<https://emodnet.eu/en>), in order to give them more visibility and include them in a wider context.

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Users can assign a persistent identifier (PID) and a global unique identifier (GUID) to the metadata through the GeoNetwork metadata catalogue, in the metadata elements "Unique resource identifier" and "File identifier". To be fully findable, the data should have a long-lasting reference (PID) ensuring that the data will remain findable over time and reduces the risk of broken links, and a globally unique string consisting of 36 characters of hexadecimal digits and hyphens (GUID) avoiding the use of the same identifier for two different digital objects (FAIR DMM WG, 2020). As DataCite member, the CNR will associate a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to the metadata forms describing datasets and products. The metadata richness is guaranteed by the inclusion in the GeoNetwork forms of all the items considered mandatory (ISO and INSPIRE rules), and by a validation process provided by the catalogue to evaluate the degree of the form completion; the inclusion of data identifier is implemented including the element Citation identifier in the metadata forms allowing the user to insert multiple identifiers to access the digital objects; the possibility of the metadata to be harvested and indexed is ensured by the GeoNetwork user interface and by the CSW provided by the catalogue.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Metadata will include elements containing all human-readable information to access the data: Resource constraints, Legal constraints and Contact for the resource. Metadata can be accessed and downloaded through the GeoNetwork user interface, while the digital objects can be visualised in the WebGIS and accessed through the metadata. If the license of the data is open, the requester can directly access the data by clicking on a link in the relative metadata form; while if the data are password protected, the requester can send an e-mail to the metadata owner/point of contact, or call by telephone to receive instructions. The data links are managed using cloud storage (NAS-QNAP) where the data provider can store the digital resources obtaining a free or password-protected URL (Uniform Resource Locator) to be included in the metadata record. The digital resources are downloadable according to a case-

specific data policy described in the metadata record, for example, indicated by the research institute, agreed inside a project or decided by the data provider. The identifier assigned to the metadata enables access to the metadata record through the standard free access protocol HTTP. Regarding the data, the URLs produced by using the cloud service resolve to a digital object accessible through the standard free access protocol HTTP. The data provider is free to manage the data requests by himself through human intervention, using the cloud storage supporting authentication and authorisation. Metadata records are guaranteed to remain accessible after data is no longer available, and the status of the data is described in the metadata element Lineage.

2.3. Making data interoperable

The knowledge is managed by the Geodatabase according to specific data models following, when possible, the INSPIRE Data Specification for spatial data (including codelists). Today, not all the vocabularies used in the GeoNetwork are documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers. Standardised formats are used for the representation of the data, that is, OGC geospatial services (WMS, WFS and WCS) allowing requests for geographical features across the web using platform-independent calls. Metadata are readable and thus interoperable for machines without any requirements thanks to the usage of standards. The geospatial records are exposed as XML (Extensible Markup Language) on the Internet (over HTTP) by a CSW. Meta(data) can be connected to other online resources through links to people (ORCID), scientific papers (DOIs), projects (webpages), or other meta(data) catalogues. In addition, metadata records can be connected to other digital objects described in the GeoNetwork through the element "Associated resources" defining also the role of the relationship (parent, service, source dataset, source catalogue, other resource).

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Concerning the quantity and the quality of metadata provided in order to enhance data reusability, license information will be included in the metadata form using the metadata elements: "Classification", "Use constraints", "Access constraints", "Other constraints" and "Credits". The reuse license is expressed as a human-readable text applying the ISO19139 codelists "MD_ClassificationCode" and "MD_RestrictionCode" (<https://standards.iso.org/iso/19139/resources/gmxCodelists.xml>) within the "MD_Constraints" element (https://wiki.esipfed.org/ISO_Constraints). Metadata include information about the provenance of the data, such as origin, history and workflow in the "Quality section", in particular in the metadata elements "Format", "Lineage" and "Process step". To ensure a cross-community understanding the metadata records are filled in English (as reported in the metadata element "Metadata language"). The standards used for metadata indicated in the elements "Metadata standard name" and "Metadata standard version" are compliant with community standards and machine-understandable. The metadata records are exposed as XML with the HTTP protocol and the CSW allows other infrastructures to automatically harvest them. The OGC geospatial services for the representation of the data in the geoportal, in other infrastructures or in desktop environments (e.g., ArcGIS, QGIS) are compliant with machine-understandable community standards (WMS, WFS, WCS) and available in the section "Distribution" of the metadata form.

3. Allocation of resources

Points to be addressed:

- Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs
- Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project
- Describe costs and potential value of long-term preservation.

To make the LIFE DREAM data FAIR, we will use the CNR-ISMAR Marine Spatial Data Infrastructure (MSDI) implemented over the years in the framework of several national and

international projects (e.g., the FP7 CoCoNet Project, the Interreg-Med AMAre Project, the Horizon 2020 EVER-EST and RELIANCE). The costs for maintaining the MSDI can be summarized as follow:

- Server, Machine warranty, External service for maintenance, Cloud storage for backup, Software license for remote access (maintenance), Specific software license (ca. 30,000 EUR/YEAR);
- Personnel cost (ca. 20,000 EUR/YEAR).

WP3, "Increasing knowledge base" leaded by CSIC, will take care of the data management. In particular, Task 3.1 - Data review, collection, integration and sharing - is in charge of CNR-ISMAR with the leadership Valentina Grande (Data Manager). This task will set the base of knowledge (geodatabase) for the PAs. It will provide a sharing point (the geoportal) where partners can visualize and access the collected spatial data, and will publish web services for the integration of the LIFE DREAM results in other platforms (OGS services and metadata). Finally, this action will draft the LIFE DREAM data policy, a crucial tool for data sharing and reuse inside and outside the project partnership. Participants: CNR (COO), UNIVPM (BEN), HCMR (BEN), CSIC (BEN), UNIBA (BEN), UNINA (BEN), SZN (BEN).

CNR predicted 28 person-month for WP3 for a total cost of 147,508 EUR. No additional costs are expected in the LIFE DREAM for maintaining the infrastructure, CNR will capitalize the MSDI implemented in previous projects [1].

[1] Foglini F., Grande V., 2022. A Marine Spatial Data Infrastructure to manage multidisciplinary, inhomogeneous and fragmented geodata in a FAIR perspective ... the Adriatic Sea experience. *Oceanologia*, Volume 65, Issue 1, 2023, Pages 260-277, ISSN 0078-3234, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceano.2022.11.002>.

4. Data security

Points to be addressed:

- Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

LIFE DREAM will ensure easy data access and data recovery, as well as, secure storage and transfer of the data. No sensitive data will be managed during the Project.

To ensure the security of the data, the following guidelines will be followed by Beneficiaries:

1) Store data in at least two separate locations to avoid loss of data; 2) Encrypt data if is deemed necessary by the participating researchers; 3) Limit the use of USB flash drivers; 4) Label files in a systematically structured way in order to ensure the final dataset coherence.

The data exchange between partners and data manager will be performed through the cloud platform offered by CNR to store documents and files guarantee service availability 7 days/week and 24h/day except during blocking incident, after which the service can be re-established within few hours.

Data access and recovery will be guaranteed thanks to the metadata catalogue inside and outside the consortium.

Long term data preservation and curation will be ensured thanks to the use of the CNR-ISMAR Marine Spatial Data Infrastructure (MSDI) and the inclusion of LIFE DREAM relevant results in European repositories, such as EMODnet and EOSC.

Management of datasets that include personal information and health information of study participants will be compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679) [1]. The GDPR is a regulation by which the European Parliament, the European Council and the European Commission intend to strengthen and unify data protection for individuals within the European Union (EU). Specific requirements for privacy and personal data protection are dealt in agreement with the document Ethics and Data protection by the European Commission [2].

[1] <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

[2] https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection_0.pdf

5. Ethical aspects

Points to be addressed:

- To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

The proposed work in LIFE DREAM will fully comply with the regulations set out in the GDPR. In addition, LIFE DREAM will comply with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, including ethical standards and guidelines, regardless country in which research is carried out. Anything in this Project shall be deemed to require a party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the party is operating. This includes any national or European regulations, rules, and norms regarding ethics in conducting research.

All project partners are obliged by European and national law (GDPR) to protect personal data. The coordinator of LIFE DREAM will follow ethical guidelines in its work. Important aspects with respect to this are:

- The ethical guidelines are based on the vision of using science and technology to create a better society and are reviewed continuously to ensure they stay up to date with developments in society and the challenges of today. They generally fall into these categories: research ethics, business ethics, and ethics in interpersonal relationships.
- All partners' employees are expected to act in accordance with the ethical guidelines and principles. As coordinator of the project, CNR will ensure that any ethical issues, which may arise, will be handled appropriately and in a transparent and fair manner.

6. Other issues

Points to be addressed:

- Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

There are no others national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management to be described.

ANNEX I

LIFE DREAM Data policy and License Agreement

Date: 31/08/2023

Authors: Valentina Grande, Federica Foglini (CNR-ISMAR)

LIFE DREAM Data policy

The LIFE DREAM Data policy is consistent with, and in the spirit of, national and international policies and laws. Applicable policies or laws are those related to UN conventions, policies of international bodies often within the UN, policies and laws of the European Union. The LIFE DREAM Data policy is intended to be fully compatible with the Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on public access to environmental information [1], the INSPIRE Directive [2], IOC [3], ICES [4], WMO [5], GCOS [6], GEOSS [7] and CLIVAR [8] data principles. LIFE DREAM makes data available freely and without restriction. "**Freely**" means at no more than the cost of reproduction and delivery, without charge for the data itself. "**Without restriction**" means without discrimination against, for example, individuals, research groups, or nationality. LIFE DREAM makes data available in a timely and easy way to users through the WebGIS platform, but LIFE DREAM data remains dependent on data contributions. The

LIFE DREAM WebGIS platform is the focus point for dissemination. According to the different types of assets, the access conditions vary: 1) metadata are freely accessible without any condition through a metadata catalogue 2) data and products require acceptance of a user license.

[1] Directive 2003/4/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2003 on public access to environmental information and repealing Council Directive 90/313/EEC (<http://ec.europa.eu/environment/aarhus/index.htm>).

[2] INSPIRE Directive for spatial information in the Community (<http://inspire.jrc.it/home.html>)

[3] IOC Data Policy (<http://ioc3.unesco.org/iode/contents.php?id=200>)

[4] ICES Data Policy 2006 (https://www.ices.dk/Datacentre/Data_Policy_2006.pdf)

[5] WMO Resolution 40 (Cg-XII; see <http://www.nws.noaa.gov/im/wmor40.htm>)

[6] Implementation plan for the Global Observing System for Climate in support of the UNFCCC, 2004; GCOS – 92, WMO/TD No.1219.

[7] Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS 10-Year Implementation Plan Reference Document (Final Draft) 2005. GEO 204. February 2005.

[8] CLIVAR Initial Implementation Plan, 1998; WCRP No. 103, WMO/TS No. 869, ICPO No. 14. June 1998.

LIFE DREAM License Agreement: Terms and Conditions

1. The Licensor grants to the Licensee a non-exclusive and non-transferable **license** to retrieve and use datasets and products from the LIFE DREAM WebGIS service in accordance with this license.
2. Retrieval, by electronic download, and the use of GIS data is free of charge, unless otherwise stipulated.
3. Regardless of whether the data are quality controlled or not, LIFE DREAM and the data source do not accept any liability for the correctness and/or appropriate interpretation of the data. Interpretation should follow scientific rules and is always the user's responsibility. Correct and appropriate data interpretation is solely the responsibility of data users.
4. Users must acknowledge data sources. It is not ethical to publish data without proper attribution or co-authorship. Any person foreseeing the use of LIFE DREAM data in a publication must communicate with the data source, in particular when the journal requires the availability of data underlying the research findings. In addition, they have to consider the data source(s) for co-authorship of published results.
5. LIFE DREAM data and products must be acknowledged using the following citation: *"Project 101074547 — LIFE21-NAT-IT-LIFE DREAM - LIFE-2021-SAP-NAT"*.
6. LIFE DREAM will invoke legal and technological measures to prevent and penalize copyright infringement.
7. Data Users should not give to third parties any LIFE DREAM data or product without prior consent from the Data Manager and Project Leader.
8. Data users must respect any and all restrictions on the use or reproduction of data. The use or reproduction of data for commercial purpose must be negotiated and require prior written

permission from the data source (the content details of which are provided within the metadata of the relevant dataset).

9. Users are requested to inform LIFE DREAM of any problems encountered with LIFE DREAM provided data. This feedback will increase the quality of the data.

10. The data cannot be used for legal, or for navigational purposes. LIFE DREAM data for products is not meant to be used for legal, economical (e.g., exploration of natural resources) or navigational purposes. It is developed solely for scientific, educational and research purposes.

11. The data provider can choose to give access to the data with an open license (Creative Commons Attribution [9]). In this case, the download of data will be guaranteed through the WebGIS without signing the LIFE DREAM data access request form.

[9][https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Creative_Commons_license#:~:text=A%20Creative%20Commons%20\(CC\)%20license,that%20the%20author%20has%20created](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Creative_Commons_license#:~:text=A%20Creative%20Commons%20(CC)%20license,that%20the%20author%20has%20created)

LIFE DREAM Data access request form

Name and Surname:

Organization:

Project name and funding organization:

Contact Information:

Data requested:

How will the data be used? (please, provide as much information as possible concerning the purpose behind the data request and foreseen future publications)

Agree to LIFE DREAM License Terms and Conditions

Date

Signature

To be sent to: lifedream@ismar.cnr.it